

Start date	01/05/2019
End date	30/04/2022
Call	H2020-SU-DRS02-2018-2019-2020 (Technologies for first responders)
Partners	19
Countries	8
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 832576.

Adapted Situation Awareness tools and tailored training scenarios for increasing capabilities and enhancing the protection of First Responders

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The main purpose of ASSISTANCE project is twofold: to help and protect different kind of first responders' (FR) organizations that work together during the mitigation of large disasters (natural or man-made) and to enhance their capabilities and skills for facing complex situations related to different types of incidents.

ASSISTANCE proposes a holistic solution that will adapt a well-tested SA application as a core of a wider SA platform, capable of offering different configuration modes for providing the tailored information outcome needed by each FR organisation, while they work together mitigating the disaster (e.g. real time video and resources location for firefighters, evacuation routes status for emergency health services and so on).

With this solution, ASSISTANCE will enhance the FRs SA during their mitigation activities through the integration of new paradigms, tools and technologies with the main objective of increasing both their protection and their efficiency.

This will be achieved by accomplishing the following operational objectives:

- + addressing the need for useful operational information via new sensors mounted on unmanned platforms or integrated in the FR's wearable equipment,
- + developing a novel SA platform, including the integration of UAV, robots and drones' swarms and innovative modules,
- + establishing the core of an advanced training network based on Virtual Reality (VR), Mixed Reality (MR) and Augmented Reality (AR) along with a set of training curricula,
- + providing a robust network infrastructure and alternative ad-hoc network capabilities based on drones' swarm for ensuring FRs and unmanned platforms connectivity,
- + validating the project results in a cost effective way under real conditions in 3 pilot demonstrations,
- + measuring the societal impact of the project and assure compliance with legal, gender and ethical EU principles and requirements.

